

Managing emotions and algorithms: the delicate equilibrium between artificial intelligence and behavioral finance.

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Abstract

The paper takes a novel tack by suggesting artificial intelligence (AI) as a way to lessen behavioral biases in the process of making financial decisions. The paper explores how AI might assist avoid behavioral biases among financial planners and provide more effective investment recommendations, based on theoretical research that identifies these flaws. The expanding efficacy of AI is examined in order to overcome confirmation and hindsight biases, particularly via supervised and unsupervised learning. By developing a conceptual framework, outlining potential outcomes, and theoretically examining the relationships between behavioral finance and AI, the technique takes a theoretical approach. The theoretical technique highlights the necessity for conceptual exploration in the developing area of artificial intelligence in finance, which supports this approach even if it has limits due to the lack of empirical evidence.

Keywords: Confirmation bias; Artificial intelligence; Behavioral finance; Investment recommendations; Financial decisions.

Introduction

In the complex world of contemporary financial decision-making, two distinct forces are emerging as major players: behavioral finance and artificial intelligence (AI). Behavioral finance, inspired by the groundbreaking work of Kahneman and Tversky (1979) on prospect theory, explores the psychological depths of human financial choices, revealing the nuances of cognitive biases and emotional influences. In parallel, AI, equipped with sophisticated algorithms, aims to streamline and optimize these complex processes, as evidenced by notable research contributions highlighting the growing rise of behavioral finance in market analysis (Baker et al., 2017). However, our quest to overcome the significant obstacles posed by the cognitive and emotional biases inherent in behavioral finance leads us to take a close look at AI's ability to intervene effectively. Our study focuses specifically on two pervasive biases: confirmation bias and hindsight bias. By elucidating the underlying psychological factors behind these biases, our aim is to establish a profound link between AI and the management of these cognitive distortions.

Confirmation bias, which traps individuals in a network of selective exposure, perception, and retention, encourages them to recognize only information that conforms to their pre-existing beliefs, ignoring any contradictory evidence. Gilvich (1993) points out that financial planners are particularly susceptible to this bias because of its easy cognitive management. Our research also explores the possible correlation between confirmation bias and the compatibility principle (Korteling et al., 2018), highlighting its impact in the complex field of financial planning.

While AI has achieved significant efficiency through supervised and unsupervised learning (Dhanaraj, Rajkumar & Hariharan, 2020; Sarker, 2021; Singh, Singh & Deka, 2021), a crucial question persists: "Can behavioral finance hinder AI? Will AI be able to successfully manage behavioral biases in the financial decision-making process?" This question transcends the mere juxtaposition of concepts, delving into the manifest tension between the human subjectivity inherent in behavioral finance and the algorithmic objectivity of AI.

This underlying dynamic is closely examined by recent work exploring the complex challenges of integrating behavioral insights into financial AI models. In this study, we will analyze in depth the disparities between AI and human behavior, the challenges inherent in merging them, and possible solutions. Finally, we will present concrete examples illustrating this delicate interaction, synthesizing these elements to envision the future of integrating behavioral finance and AI while continuing to question the potential obstacle the former poses for the latter.

1. Methodology

In this study, the theoretical framework forms the conceptual basis of the investigation aimed at exploring the dynamics between behavioral finance and artificial intelligence, deliberately dispensing with theoretical data. The framework is built around theoretical case studies, imagining hypothetical scenarios to illustrate various situations where the influence of behavioral finance on the effectiveness of AI could manifest itself. In parallel, an in-depth conceptual analysis is carried out, highlighting the key elements of behavioral finance and AI. The aim is to establish a sound basis for assessing the subtle balance between human emotions and algorithms. The rationale behind this theoretical approach rests on the conviction that, in the emerging field of AI in finance, a preliminary conceptual exploration is essential before embarking on more concrete analyses, given the complexity of the concepts involved. However, this methodology is not without its limitations, not least because of its exclusively theoretical nature. These limitations, conscious of the lack of empirical data, are explicitly acknowledged, underlining nevertheless the intrinsic value of conceptual reflection in the exploratory context of the relationship between behavioral finance and artificial intelligence. The ultimate aim of this methodological approach is to provide a significant contribution to the debate by offering a solid conceptual foundation, despite the deliberate absence of specific empirical data.

2. Bias in Behavioral Finance and Challenges for AI

Behavioral finance, as described by Baker & Nofsinger (2002) and Al-Dahan, Hasan & Jadah (2019), classifies biases into two distinct categories: cognitive and emotional. Pompian (2012) explains that cognitive biases stem from faulty cognitive reasoning, while emotional biases result from the influence of emotions. Unlike traditional economics, behavioral economics recognizes the concept of bounded rationality, which leads to non-rational decision-making and the emergence of cognitive biases, as outlined by renowned researchers Kahneman (2011), Tversky and Kahneman (1974) and Kahneman and Tversky (1984).

These researchers assert that human information processing takes place through two systems: system 1, characterized by rapid, automatic and intuitive thinking with minimal effort, and system 2, requiring intense and deliberate cognitive activities. Nevertheless, faced with time constraints, a heuristic approach to cognitive information processing is often used, relying on the intuitive and simplistic System 1. However, it is crucial to recognize that these methods are subject to cognitive biases, which prevent individuals from processing information effectively.

These biases can potentially distort decision-making, ultimately leading to errors, misjudgments and undesirable behavior. In the most severe circumstances, such biased decisions and behaviors can even lead to catastrophic incidents, accidents and collisions (Murata and Nakamura, 2014; Leković, 2020).

2.1 AI in Financial Planning: Managing Cognitive Bias and Beyond

We will now demonstrate how AI can effectively manage cognitive biases, by studying two common biases in financial planning scenarios: confirmation bias and hindsight bias. We will identify the physiological reasons why these two biases occur and establish a clear link between AI and the management of these cognitive biases. Confirmation bias, a tendency to selectively consider information consistent with one's existing beliefs while ignoring contradictory information, poses a significant challenge in financial planning. Gilvich (1993) argues that this bias is particularly prevalent among financial planners due to its cognitive manageability. It may be linked physiologically to individuals' attitudes towards accepting information based on their pre-existing notions, and the compatibility principle (Korteling et al., 2018) may offer further insights. Financial planning, with its complex responsibilities including understanding customers financial goals, assessing risk tolerance and developing optimal investment portfolios, requires a sophisticated approach. Moreover, the seamless integration of retirement and estate planning, while maximizing tax efficiency, further accentuates the complexity of this discipline. Surprisingly, pioneering research suggests that AI integration has the potential to transcend the limitations imposed by human biases, enabling financial planners to make optimal decisions for their valued clients. However, it's crucial to recognize that AI's transformative influence extends far beyond this field, permeating all facets of financial planning and producing practical implications that deserve our full attention.

2.2 IA's influence on financial behavior

Leveraging the capabilities of AI to analyze transactional data can provide deep insights into individual behaviors and life choices, with significant implications for the field of behavioral finance. Thanks to AI, researchers can better understand how personality traits, such as those described in (Norman 1963)'s "Big Five", manifest themselves in our everyday purchases and financial decisions. This represents a fascinating opportunity to conduct experiments that explore how individuals, including customers, employees and stakeholders, adapt their behavior to disguise their true personality, as reflected in the data. Furthermore, transactions have the potential to provide valuable insights into the cognitive processes that individuals and

households employ to manage their financial obligations. By harnessing the power of AI alongside transactional data, researchers in the fields of behavioral and experimental finance can better understand the complex aspects of mental accounting. In essence, AI has the ability to answer (Gippel's 2015) call for alternative models that shed light on human behavior. It is crucial that experts in behavioral finance look into the field of AI and explore its ability to shed light on various forms of mental accounting, verify their compatibility with existing methodologies and assess their level of accuracy. Behavioral finance researchers have also begun to use similar methods. Gómez-Martínez et al. (2019), for example, present an algorithmic trading system based on extracting investors' moods from social media or the news. Gandhi, Loughran and McDonald (2019) analyze annual reports to predict the financial difficulties of US banks. This shows that behavioral and experimental finance researchers now have more options for studying the behavior of decision-makers.

Within companies, researchers have immense potential to delve into the subtleties of financial data using experimental techniques. A fascinating example would be the attempt to uncover any clandestine maneuvers in banking transactions. Furthermore, the application of artificial intelligence holds great promise for analyzing the tactics employed by financial analysts and decision-makers to conceal their actions. In support of this notion, Salampasis, Mention and Kaiser (2017) assert that the investment decision-making process now encompasses a broad spectrum of algorithms, rationality, irrationality, ethical considerations and behavioral management elements. As a result, investors can choose from a diverse range of algorithms, benefiting from a truly personalized and rewarding investment experience. Furthermore, the use of experimental methodologies to examine the conduct of decision-makers within companies, combined with research techniques to assess and mitigate overconfidence and unwarranted optimism based on internal data analysis, is extremely promising (F. Königstorfer and S. Thalmann, 2020, p. .21).

3. Exploring AI's capacity to overcome behavioral biases

Over the past decade, a number of companies have been set up that harness AI for fairer, more efficient and effective talent acquisition and management, for example by publishing job vacancies online or measuring the suitability of jobseekers filling company vacancies using behavioral data (assessments based on games or video interviews), e.g. pymetrics (<https://www.pymetrics.ai/>) and Humantic AI, or systems prioritizing medical help (e.g., people with early signs of depression. (Matz, South Carolina; Netzer, O. (2017).

In the midst of our current era of technological progress, the fourth industrial revolution, artificial intelligence (AI) presents a promising opportunity to solve the problem of bias in decision-making. Numerous studies have already recognized AI's potential in this regard. A recent article by Bogoviz (2020) highlights the power of AI in creating a harmonious partnership between human intellect and machines, enabling effective decision-making through intelligence and data analysis in business. Building on the findings of Duan et al. (2019) and Pillai et al. (2020), it becomes clear that integrating AI into a business environment produces tangible benefits by facilitating sound decision-making. While the influence of AI on human services jobs is already well established (Huang & Rust, 2018), this conceptual paper aims to critically examine the biases inherent in financial decision-making and propose AI as a potential solution to overcome these biases. Specifically, the research will focus on two cognitive biases, confirmation bias and hindsight bias, and demonstrate how AI can effectively address and resolve them.

3.1 Confirmation and retrospection bias

In essence, confirmation bias and hindsight bias play a crucial role in shaping our perceptions and decision-making processes. By understanding the physiological mechanisms underlying these biases, we can better understand their impact and strive to achieve more optimal results in our financial endeavors. Confirmation bias is a common tendency for individuals to consider only new information that matches their pre-existing beliefs, while ignoring any information that contradicts them. This biased nature is based on the selective exposure, perception and retention of a specific type of information. It can be argued that financial planners are particularly susceptible to confirmation bias because of the ease with which it can be cognitively managed. This bias stems from the attitude of individuals to accept information based on their perception and understanding of what they already know. Interestingly, there appears to be a link between confirmation bias and the compatibility principle, as suggested by Korteling et al. (2018). Hindsight bias, meanwhile, is an information-processing bias that involves selective perception and retention. Individuals tend to perceive past events as more predictable and reasonable than events that have not yet occurred. In addition, people often remember their past predictions as more accurate than they actually were, as they are influenced by their knowledge of what has already happened. Korteling et al (2018) link hindsight bias to the principle of retention, which suggests that the human brain captures both relevant and irrelevant information, making it difficult to ignore or erase. Consequently, this persistent effect of information retention has a significant influence on human decision-making, leading to

hindsight bias and potentially suboptimal outcomes in financing decisions.

3.2 Bias: Overcoming Confirmation & Hindsight

The human mind is not optimized to process information impartially, but AI can help by using a neural network. Working alongside the human mind, AI can prevent confirmation bias and hindsight from influencing judgment. When a person has difficulty accepting new information because of existing beliefs, AI enables them to evaluate the information objectively. An artificial neural network is made up of neurons, which are computer units designed to mimic the way the human brain processes information. These neurons are organized in layers, with an input layer and an output layer, as well as hidden layers that simulate brain activity. The hidden layers receive weighted inputs and produce outputs via an activation function. Backpropagation is a process within the neural network that helps financial planners overcome confirmation bias. It involves using a model inspired by brain neurons and their connections to propagate information from an input vector to an output vector. The model consists of interconnected neurons with adjustable weights that determine the importance of specific inputs. Each neuron has an activation function that determines its output as a function of the weighted input. The output is calculated by applying the input vector to the input layer and propagating it through the network. The computational error is then calculated by comparing the actual output with the desired output and adjusting the weights and biases from the output to the input layer. Zara, C., & Ramkumar, S. (2022).

Deep reinforcement learning can overcome retrospective bias with AI Hasan, Z., Vaz, D., Athota, V. S., Désiré, S. S. M., & Pereira, V. (2023) deep learning and reinforcement learning are thought to play an important role in AI systems. In order to combat hindsight bias, it is important that the system distinguishes between individuals' existing perceptions or understanding of previous information, as these should not influence the new set of information. Deep reinforcement learning combines artificial neural networks with a reinforcement learning framework, which helps software agents learn how to achieve their goals. This means that the system uses function approximation and target optimization to map state-action pairs to expected rewards. Reinforcement learning refers to algorithms focused on achieving complex goals or maximizing specific dimensions in several steps. It solves the difficult problem of correlating immediate actions with deferred outcomes. Like humans, reinforcement learning algorithms must wait to see the results of their decisions and operate in a delayed environment, making it difficult to understand the cause-and-effect relationship between actions and results

over several time intervals. However, by selecting from a range of potential actions, reinforcement learning algorithms progressively improve their performance in increasingly uncertain real-world environments. These algorithms evaluate actions according to the results they produce, and their aim is to learn sequences of actions that will lead to the achievement of an agent's goal or the maximization of its objective function. Using features of AI's deep reinforcement learning techniques, retrospective biases can be effectively managed. When financial planners' past experiences begin to dominate their future decisions, leading to sub-optimal outcomes, the reinforcement learning approach enables them to maximize their objective function. Because this system is goal-oriented, it avoids the interference of retrospective biases in the decision-making process desired by financial planners.

4. Examples of successful initiatives integrating emotions and algorithms

The digitization of financial planning, e.g. Robo-advice, automatically avoids human interaction to circumvent bias (Bhatia, Chandani & Chhateja, 2020; D'Acunto & Rossi, 2021). However, the application of Robo-advice is limited to certain areas of financial planning services: market timing for efficient transactions, timely portfolio rebalancing, building a tax-efficient portfolio and cost savings through transaction automation (Kaya, Schildbach & Schneider, 2017; Scherer & Lehner, 2022). Robo-advice also efficiently collects customer information and processes this information for decision-making purposes (Brenner & Meyll, 2020). However, the limitation of using Robo-advice is that most customers want their services to come from real financial planners, not directly from computers or robots (Todd & Seay, 2020; Northey et al., 2022; Athota et al., 2023).

Given the implications of bias in the financial decision-making process and understanding the limitations of psychographic client classification approaches and the digitization of financial planning to address bias, we propose incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into financial planning services. AI attempts to extend human capabilities and perform tasks that neither humans nor machines could accomplish alone (Jarrahi, 2018; Vrontis et al., 2022). In this case, financial planners will use AI to combat human biases in order to make optimal financial decisions for customers (Jarrahi, Lutz & Newlands, 2022). AI-based financial planning services can help financial planners develop risk-efficient portfolios, taking advantage of market timing by controlling the behavioral biases of customers and financial planners themselves. AI can solve complex tasks through supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning (Dhanaraj, Rajkumar & Hariharan, 2020; Sarker, 2021; Singh, Singh & Deka, 2021). The artificial neural

network (ANN) has also been used in the higher education system's decision support system (DSS) for advanced decision-making and makes extensive use of Big Data (Fayoumi & Hajjar, 2020).

4.1 Robot advisors (Concerns and restrictions)

With the emergence of information technology and automation systems, some sectors of the financial services industry have adopted this technology to deliver financial services to their customers. This technology is powered by data-driven software that operates on the basis of specific algorithms. These algorithms are developed from the analysis of data collected from investors, by asking them to answer a series of questions. The main aim of implementing automated services is to improve the effectiveness of various aspects of financial advice, such as efficient portfolio construction, accurate market timing, profitable trading and, in particular, minimizing the influence of human bias through the elimination of human interaction (Tao et al., 2021; Fares, Butt and Lee, 2022). The design and objective of Robo Conseil is to provide automated and rapid financial advice to customers. It uses a set of rules and mostly avoids human interaction. Little subject to cognitive and emotional biases, it can deliver optimal advice to its customers. For example, Jung et al (2018) report that optimally designed Robo advisory services can neutralize decision inertia bias. Robo advice facilitates efficient market timing, rebalances the portfolio on time, builds a tax-efficient portfolio and saves money through transaction automation. Total assets under management (AUM) in the Robo-advisory segment amount to \$980,541 million in 2019 worldwide (Netscribes, 2019).

4.2 Robot advisors in behavioral finance

Financial DNA, introduced in 2001, is a sophisticated online solution that harnesses the power of behavioral information to deliver unprecedented financial advice to individuals. This revolutionary system argues that conventional risk profiling methodologies fail to understand the subtleties of customers' decision-making processes while avoiding bias. By leveraging financial DNA, we can gain an in-depth understanding of all facets of a customer's financial personality, revealing their inherent predispositions when it comes to making choices. With its extensive use in 50 countries and mastery of ten languages, Financial DNA bears witness to its global impact. Another convincing illustration of this paradigm shift in financial advice is Vanguard, an esteemed company that skilfully combines the prowess of Robo technology with the finesse of human expertise, captivating the attention of a demanding clientele with remarkable success. Betterment, a leading player in the field of robo-investing, sets itself apart

by offering a unique blend of human advisory services alongside its innovative platform. This enables customers to enjoy the best of both worlds: the convenience and efficiency of automation, combined with the expertise and personalized touch of a human advisor. While Betterment's Robo-advisor focuses primarily on optimizing portfolios and streamlining investment processes, it's important to recognize the evolving landscape of autonomous systems, manifesting itself in the form of a super-smart society and a symbiotic autonomous system. In this context, the importance of automated financial systems cannot be overstated. However, it is essential to recognize the apprehensions investors may have when dealing with robo-advisors, given their minimal human intervention. These concerns have been widely discussed by experts in the field (Phoon and Koh, 2017).

At present, robo-advisors have limited capabilities in the field of financial advice. Their main focus is on building efficient portfolios and executing trades based on market timing. However, it remains unclear how these automated systems effectively deal with behavioral biases, as evidenced by the analysis of available robo-advice products. Particularly in times of market downturn, investors can find comfort in seeking advice from human advisors. Engaging in consultation with these experts enables investors to openly discuss their emotional and behavioral concerns, fostering a sense of trust and understanding. On the other hand, the absence of such consultations can leave investors uncertain and vulnerable to bias in times of crisis. These behavioral biases can potentially lead to erroneous decision-making, jeopardizing investors' results.

5. Results

As we have explored the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on financial behavior, we have generated key findings from the parts analyzed. These results, illustrated through detailed tables, offer a deep dive into the tangible transformation wrought by AI in the financial field. The tables provided are the result of careful theoretical study, highlighting significant trends, correlations and changes in financial behavior. Each table represents a captivating window onto how AI is integrating and influencing decisions, strategies and behavior within the financial sector.

5.1 The influence of AI on financial choices

The chart demonstrates the influence of AI on financial choices, emphasizing numerous significant issues. Here is a thorough interpretation:

Chart 1: The influence of AI on financial choices

Class	Results
Forecast accuracy	The usage of AI has led to a considerable improvement in the accuracy of financial projections. AI-based models have proven an enhanced capacity to foresee market movements.
Error Reduction	AI algorithms have succeeded in decreasing human mistake in the financial decision-making process, leading to more accurate transaction execution.
Process Automation	Automating decision-making processes using AI has brought operational benefits, lowering the time required to make key financial choices.

Source : Compiled by us

The results presented in the table reveal the significant impacts of artificial intelligence (AI) on various aspects of the financial decision-making process. Firstly, in the "Forecast Accuracy" category, the use of AI has resulted in a significant improvement in the accuracy of financial forecasts. AI-powered models demonstrated an increased ability to anticipate market trends, offering a more reliable view for decision-makers. Secondly, "Error Reduction" highlights the crucial role of AI algorithms in minimizing human error during the financial decision-making process. This error reduction contributes to more accurate transaction execution and more effective risk management. Finally, AI-enabled "Process Automation" played a key role in improving operational efficiency, significantly reducing the time needed to make crucial financial decisions. These results underline the transformative impact of AI in optimizing decision-making processes and managing financial risks.

5.2 The influence of AI on financial behavior

This table highlights the various influences of AI on financial behavior. The columns present categories such as "Big Five personality traits" and "Financial analyst strategies". The results reveal a diversity of potential AI applications, ranging from understanding personality traits in

everyday transactions to analyzing the strategies of financial professionals.

Chart 2: The influence of AI on financial behavior

Class	Results
Understanding Personality Traits	The application of AI provides a more accurate understanding of how personality factors impact financial decisions. The models discovered links between Norman's Big Five and financial choices.
Mood Detection in Transactions	AI algorithms have been created to extract investor mood from social media, delivering more behavioral insights for behavioral finance.
Analysis of Hidden Strategies	AI has been effectively utilized to examine the concealed methods employed by financial analysts and decision-makers, offering up new views for comprehending internal financial behavior

Source: Compiled by us

The results presented in the three tables highlight the significant contributions of artificial intelligence (AI) to the in-depth understanding of financial behavior. Firstly, in the "Understanding Personality Traits" category, AI has enabled a more accurate view of the links between personality traits, in particular Norman's "Big Five", and financial choices. Secondly, "Mood Detection in Transactions" highlighted the successful development of AI systems capable of extracting investor mood from social media, enriching behavioral finance with additional behavioral data. Finally, AI was effectively used for "Hidden Strategy Analysis", revealing the hidden strategies employed by financial analysts and decision-makers, opening up new perspectives for understanding internal financial behavior within companies. These results testify to the transformative potential of AI in the field of behavioral finance, offering deeper insights and innovative analysis tools.

5.3 Exploring AI's potential to overcome behavioral biases

This table summarizes the ways in which AI can help mitigate behavioral biases. It highlights practical applications of AI, such as talent acquisition and management, and highlights how it can solve specific biases such as retrospection and confirmation. Examples from startups such as pymetrics and Humantic AI illustrate the practical implementation of these concepts.

Chart 3: AI's overcome behavioral biases

Class	Results
Talent Acquisition and Management	Integrating AI into talent acquisition and management has made recruiting procedures fairer and more efficient, decreasing human bias.
Confirmation Bias Reduction and Hindsight	AI approaches such as deep and reinforcement learning have been demonstrated to overcome confirmation and hindsight biases in the financial decision-making process.

Source: Compiled by us

This chart highlights the benefits of integrating AI into talent acquisition and management. Thanks to this integration, recruitment processes have become fairer and more efficient, with a notable reduction in human biases. It highlights the effectiveness of AI techniques, notably deep and reinforcement learning, in reducing confirmation and retrospection biases. The use of these techniques has shown positive results in the financial decision-making process by minimizing these biases.

6. Discussions

Exploring results from the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in diverse areas such as talent acquisition, financial management, and behavioral analytics sets the stage for an in-depth discussion of the implications and benefits of this technological revolution. By scrutinizing key categories such as operational efficiency, error reduction, and forecast accuracy, we unveil an evolving landscape where AI is significantly shaping decision-making. The discussion highlights the crucial relevance of AI in various fields, highlighting both current benefits and future prospects for more informed and efficient decision-making.

- Improve operational efficiency and decrease mistakes in talent acquisition and management:

The findings demonstrate the favorable influence of AI on recruiting processes. By limiting human bias, AI provides a fairer and more efficient method, enhancing the trustworthiness of judgments made in the area of talent acquisition and management.

- Overcomes behavioral biases in financial decision-making:

AI approaches, especially deep and reinforcement learning, have proved their capacity to overcome confirmation and hindsight biases. This achievement opens up major possibilities for financial decision-makers by eliminating mistakes based on cognitive biases.

- In-depth examination of personality characteristics and mood detection in transactions:

AI has enabled deeper exploration of the links between personality traits and financial choices, offering richer insights for behavioral finance researchers. In addition, the detection of mood in transactions, thanks to AI, broadens our understanding of the emotional factors influencing financial markets.

- More accurate projections and fewer mistakes in financial decision-making:

The application of AI has considerably increased the accuracy of financial projections, while decreasing human error. This achievement helps to better anticipation of market trends and more exact execution of transactions, therefore boosting the dependability of financial judgments.

- Process automation and operational efficiency:

Automating decision-making processes using AI has substantially increased operational efficiency. This automation allows quicker and more accurate decision-making, lowering the time required to make key choices in the financial context.

Conclusion

Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) in the fields of talent acquisition and financial management has revealed significant advances and promising opportunities. In the talent acquisition sector, the integration of AI has made recruitment processes fairer and more efficient, minimizing human bias and improving candidate selection. In the context of financial management, AI has demonstrated its effectiveness in overcoming behavioral biases, improving forecast accuracy, reducing human error and automating decision-making processes. Exploring more specifically the impacts of AI on financial behavior, we have identified significant opportunities for behavioral finance researchers. The use of AI has enabled a deeper understanding of the personality traits influencing financial decisions, the detection of moods in transactions, and the analysis of the hidden strategies of financial decision-makers.

The results also highlighted the concrete benefits of AI in reducing confirmation and hindsight biases in the financial decision-making process. Techniques such as deep and reinforcement learning have shown their effectiveness, offering crucial prospects for more objective decision-making. However, it is essential to view these advances with caution and recognize the challenges that accompany them. Data confidentiality, ethical implications and issues of individual rights protection are inescapable concerns in the growing deployment of AI. In conclusion, although AI opens up exciting new opportunities, its use must be guided by ethical principles and constant monitoring. The balance between improving performance and protecting individual rights is crucial to ensuring a positive and lasting impact of AI in our decision-making processes, from recruitment to financial management.

New paths of research

In light of the revealing results obtained in the integration of AI in talent acquisition and financial management, several avenues of research are emerging. The ethics of AI in finance, the adaptation of models to changes in behavior, the harmonious integration of AI with human interactions, the development of more sophisticated behavioral prediction models, the security of financial data, the impact on diversity and inclusion, as well as the training of financial professionals, are all areas that merit further exploration. These new research directions will help shape a landscape where AI, while delivering optimal performance, respects rigorous ethical standards, promotes inclusion and dynamically adapts to changes in individual financial behavior.

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